

EXPERIMENTAL STUDY ON ANTI-PENETRATION PERFORMANCE OF SANDWICH TARGET MADE OF THIN STEEL PLATES AND WOOD AGAINST 7.62MM BULLET

He Liling^{1,2}, Zhong Weizhou^{1,2}, Lv Ming^{1,2}, Zhang Fangju^{1,2}, Wei Fayuan¹ and Yue Xiaohong¹

¹ Institute of Systems Engineering, China Academy of Engineering Physics, Mianyang, Sichuan, 621999, China

² Shock and Vibration of Engineering Materials and Structures Key Laboratory of Sichuan Province, Mianyang, Sichuan, 621999, China

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ABSTRACT

The sandwich structure made of thin steel plates and wood is commonly used as cushion structure, through which the impact load could reduce the peak value and increase the duration time and then protect the object enwrapped inside. However, the object inside may confront high-speed bullet or fragment, which has the distinct characteristic as local impact and could damage the object. It is necessary to study the anti-penetration performance of the sandwich structure. In the present manuscript, the sandwich structure made of thin steel plates and wood is shot by 7.62mm ordinary bullet fired by rifle.

Two types of steel plates made of 06Cr19Ni10 and 30CrMoA are shot by bullets. The test indicates that the bullet perforates the steel plate with thickness 4mm and 8mm but stopped in front of the 16mm 30CrMoA steel plate. According to the law of energy conservation, the ballistic limit velocities are 511.7m/s, 498.6m/s and 684.3m/s for 4mm, 8mm 06Cr19Ni10 and 8mm 30CrMoA steel plates, separately.

The 7.62mm ordinary bullet could not perforate the sandwich target in the present paper. The bullet applies circumferential pressure along the penetration trajectory. No tearing surface appears in the longitudinal wood after penetration but the weak bonding surface devulves in the transverse wood. The dissection of wood after penetration exhibits that the transverse fibres are broken in transverse wood and the fibres are pushed aside in the longitudinal wood along the ballistic trajectory. The Depth of Penetration (DOP) in longitudinal wood is higher than that in the transverse wood. Based on the dynamic cavity expansion model, the dynamic compressive strength of the transverse and longitudinal wood are fitted as 107.9MPa and 67.7MPa, separately, which quantitatively represents that the anti-penetration ability of transverse wood is better than that of the longitudinal wood.

1 INTRODUCTION

The object transported by the automobile or airplane may confront impact loading and high temperature environment in the traffic accident. It is necessary to design the container to protect the object inside from the damage caused by the shock and heat in the accident, such as the transport container for the spent fuel^[1], et al. For the impact load, the main function of the container is to cushion the object inside, which means that the force transmitted to the object inside must have smaller peak value and longer duration time. The sandwich structure is ordinarily used as the cushion structure. The common composition of the sandwich structure is two thin sheets with buffer material inside.

The buffer material should have long stress plateau when it is compressed, such as the foamed aluminium^[2, 3], wood^[4, 5], et al. For example, the wood has up to 60% compressive strain when the stress stays in the plateau. It is the reason that the wood is commonly used as the buffer material. In meso scale, the wood is mainly comprised of parallel fibres and soft bonding matrix, which is a typical natural composite material and has the macro-mechanical behaviour as transverse isotropy. For the clear, the transverse wood indicates that the load is perpendicular to the fibre direction and the

longitudinal wood parallel to the fibre direction. The overall bearing capacity of the longitudinal wood is better than that of the transverse wood^[5].

Besides the traffic accident, the high-speed bullets and fragments could also destroy the object inside the container. Different from the bearing capacity of the overall cushion structure, the penetration process dramatically reduces the loading area and the local bearing capacity should be studied. In the present paper, the sandwich structure made of two thin steel plates with wood inside is shot by the 7.62mm ordinary bullet. The anti-penetration performance of the structure is investigated, and the anti-penetration mechanism is also analysed.

2 DESIGNATION OF GUN SHOT TEST

2.1 7.62mm ordinary bullet

The 7.62mm ordinary bullet is adopted in the present paper. The bullet is mounted in the cartridge, as shown in Fig. 1. The bullet and cartridge is called as the warhead in the present paper. The mass of warhead is 16.5g and its length is 55.6mm. The warhead is fired by the rifle shown in Fig. 2. The propellant power in the cartridge case pushed the bullet to move forward with velocity $750\pm 30\text{m/s}$. The high-speed bullet penetrates into the target. The mass of the bullet is approximately 8g and its length and diameter are almost 26mm and 7.9mm, separately. The bullet is mainly comprised of copper clad steel jacket, lead filler and mild steel core^[6]. Its schematic is shown in Fig. 3. The mass of the core is 3.6g. Its length and diameter are 19.7mm and 5.8mm, separately.

Figure 1: 7.62mm ordinary bullet with cartridge case.

Figure 2: Firing rifle.

Figure 3: Schematic of the bullet.

2.2 Target

The sandwich target made of steel plates and wood is the main object to be studied in the present paper. The front steel plate is made of 06Cr19Ni10 steel and the back is 30CrMoA. The transverse or longitudinal wood is placed inside. The target configuration is shown in Fig. 4. The cross section of the sandwich target is a circle with diameter 120mm, which is 15 times of the diameter of bullet. The quasi-static mechanical properties of 30CrMoA and 06Cr19Ni10 steels are listed in Table 1. It is indicated that the strength of 30CrMoA is higher than that of 06Cr19Ni10, but both of its ductility and impact toughness are little lower than that of 06Cr19Ni10.

Figure 4: Configuration of the sandwich target

Name	Density g/cm ³	Elastic Modulus GPa	Poisson's Ratio	Yield Strength MPa	Cross- section Reduction %	Impact Toughness kJ/m ²	Fracture Strength MPa
30CrMoA	7.82	209	0.27	735	~50	~710	930
06Cr19Ni10	7.82	205	0.33	210	~75	>2500	520

Table 1: Quasi-static mechanical properties of 06Cr19Ni10 and 30CrMoA steels

The thin steel plates which bound the wood are firstly investigated. Simply, only the conclusions for the thin steel plates are listed in the present paper in order to restrict the paper in required length. The combination of the sandwich targets studied in the present paper are listed in Table 2.

Target Type	Configuration
Single steel plate	06Cr19Ni10(4)*
	06Cr19Ni10(8)
	30CrMoA(8)
	30CrMoA(16)
Sandwich target	06Cr19Ni10(4)+Wood(Transverse 200)+30CrMoA(8)
	06Cr19Ni10(8)+Wood(Transverse 200)+30CrMoA(8)
	06Cr19Ni10(4)+Wood(Longitudinal 200)+30CrMoA(8)
	06Cr19Ni10(4)+Wood(Transverse 160)+30CrMoA(16)
	06Cr19Ni10(4)+Wood(Longitudinal 160)+30CrMoA(16)

*The number in () represents the thickness of steel or wood thickness with unit mm;

**“+” indicates that steel and wood are placed without space.

Table 2: Configuration of targets

2.3 Layout of Test

The bullet is fired by rifle. The gun is placed away from the target surface with a distance about 15m. The muzzle velocity of the bullet is recorded by E9900-X High-precision shooting chronograph. The bullet normally impacts the target. The bullet gesture and its residual velocity are recorded by high-speed photography. The target simply placed on a frame. The layout of the test is shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Experimental layout

3 TEST RESULTS AND ANALYSES

19 shots were carried out in the present paper with 10 shots for single steel plates and 9 shots for sandwich targets. The test results are listed in Tables 3 and 4. It is indicated that the bullet could not perforated the 16mm thick 30CrMoA steel plate and all sandwich targets in the present paper. The recovery bullets and plugs are shown in Fig. 6. It is indicated that the 8mm thick steel plates are perforated by ductile hole-enlargement and plugging.

Based on the energy and momentum conservation laws, assuming the projectile as rigid body, the Recht-Ipson model is constructed^[7, 8]. The relationship between the impact and residual velocity could be represented as follows.

$$V_r = \frac{1}{1 + \lambda} \sqrt{V_0^2 - V_{bl}^2} \quad (1)$$

In Equation (1), V_r is the residual velocity of bullet. λ is the ratio of the effective plug mass m^* and the projectile mass M , $M = 8\text{g}$. $\lambda=0$ when no plugging is formed. V_0 is the impact velocity of bullet. V_{bl} is the ballistic limit velocity of target. The effective plug mass is represented as

$$m^* = m \left(\frac{V_{pl}}{V_r} \right)^2 \quad (2)$$

Here m is the plug mass and V_{pl} is the translation velocity of the plug. Restricted by the numbers of the recovery plugs, we assume that the 8mm 30CrMoA steel plate has 5.1g plug and 8mm 06Cr19Ni10 steel plate has 2.9g plug, respectively.

Based on Equations (1) and (2), the ballistic limit velocity is fitted by the experimental data of single plates, as shown in Fig. 7. The ballistic limit velocities for the 4mm and 8mm 06Cr19Ni10 steel plates and 8mm 30CrMoA steel plates are 511.7m/s, 498.6m/s and 684.3m/s, respectively. The strength of target material dominates the anti-penetration performance when the target undergoes the similar failure mode. The unusual decrease of ballistic limit velocity with target thickness increase is related to the transformation of target failure mode from ductile hole-enlargement to combination of ductile hole-enlargement and plugging.

Case No.	Target Material	Target Thickness mm	Impact Velocity m/s	Residual Velocity m/s		Residual Mass g		
				Bullet	Plug	Core	Plug	
S-3	30CrMoA	8.06	744	147	171	3.6	-	
S-4		7.97	760	210	243	3.6	-	
S-25		7.93	771	177	192	-	-	
S-26		8.03	760	183	209	3.6	5.1	
S-9		15.96	751	NOT Perforated		3.6	-	
S-10		15.95	753	NOT Perforated		3.4	-	
S-15		3.91	745	551	-	-	-	
S-16		3.97	744	578	-	-	-	
S-21		06Cr19Ni10	7.99	753	406	436	-	-
S-22			8.00	738	378	402	-	-

Table 3: Experimental results of single steel plate

The transverse wood in sandwich target after penetration is shown in Fig. 8. It reveals that the bullet would devulves the weak surface of the transverse wood after though 4mm 06Cr19Ni10 steel plate. The delamination surface is approximately parallel to the fiber direction in the transverse wood, such as M-3, M-5, M-15 and M-16. After through 8mm 06Cr19Ni10 steel plate, the transverse wood exhibits several cracks passing through the impact point, such as M-4.

The delamination surface in the transverse wood expands along the projectile moving direction. It separates the wood into two halves when the thickness of wood is 160mm. However, the bonding

constraint of the back surface restricted the tearing of the delamination surface to the location where the bullet stopped, when the thickness of the wood is 200mm.

The generation of the tearing surface indicates that there exists circumferential expansion pressure along the ballistic trajectory. As long as the circumferential pressure is big enough, the weak bonding surface of the transverse wood, i.e., the surface parallel to the fiber direction, would devulse, for the strength of fiber is much higher than that of the matrix in wood. However, the circumferential expansion force could not break the fibers and devulse another tearing surface.

Case No.	Target Material	Target Thickness mm	Impact Velocity m/s	DOP in Wood mm	Residual Mass g	
					Core	Plug
M-3	06Cr19Ni10	4.08	749	117	-	-
	Transverse wood	195.5				
M-4	30CrMoA	7.96	754	84	3.6	2.9
	06Cr19Ni10	7.98				
M-5	Transverse wood	195.2	756	144	3.6	-
	30CrMoA	7.93				
M-9	06Cr19Ni10	4.10	750	168	-	-
	Transverse wood	195.0				
M-10	30CrMoA	8.00	771	Perforated	3.6	-
	06Cr19Ni10	3.89				
M-15	Longitudinal wood	199.1	753	128	3.6	-
	30CrMoA	7.95				
M-16	06Cr19Ni10	4.00	753	136	3.6	-
	Longitudinal wood	199.3				
M-21	30CrMoA	7.96	779	Perforated	3.4	-
	06Cr19Ni10	3.99				
M-22	Transverse wood	155.8	771	Perforated	3.6	-
	30CrMoA	15.94				
	06Cr19Ni10	3.94				
	Transverse wood	155.0				
	30CrMoA	15.98				
	06Cr19Ni10	4.11				
	Longitudinal wood	159.2				
	30CrMoA	15.98				
	06Cr19Ni10	3.99				
	Longitudinal wood	159.4				
	30CrMoA	16.00				

Table 4: Experimental results of the sandwich targets

Figure 6: Recovery bullet and the plugs

Figure 7: Comparison of the test data and theoretical prediction

(a) Impact surface, M-3, M-4, M-5 from left to right

(b) Back surface, M-3, M-4, M-5 from left to right

(c) Target side surface, bullet penetrates from right to left. M-3, M-4, M-5 from left to right

(d) Impact surface, M-15, M-16 from left to right

(e) Back surface, M-15, M-16 from left to right

(f) Target side surface, bullet penetrates from right to left. M-15, M-16 from left to right

Figure 8: Transverse wood after shot

The longitudinal wood is shown in Fig. 9 after shot by bullet through 4mm 06Cr19Ni10 steel plate. All woods are perforated except M-9. Obviously, there are no cracks through the impact point. The surfaces parallel to the penetration path has similar bonding strength, since they are all bounded by the soft matrix. The circumferential pressure is still not big enough to open any of the bounding surfaces.

(a) Impact surface, M-9, M-10 from left to right

(b) Back surface, M-9, M-10 from left to right

(c) Target side surface, bullet penetrates from right to left. M-9, M-10 from left to right

(d) Impact surface, M-21, M-22 from left to right

(e) Back surface, M-21, M-22 from left to right

(f) Target side surface, bullet penetrates from right to left. M-21, M-22 from left to right

Figure 9: Longitudinal wood after shot

The wood is dissected along the ballistic trajectory, as shown in Fig. 10. The average Depths of Penetration (DOP) in transverse and longitudinal woods are 130mm~132mm and 160mm~184mm, respectively. The bullet must cut the fibers to proceed in the transverse wood. However, the bullet only has to push the soft matrix material aside in order to penetrate the longitudinal wood. That's the reason that the transverse wood has better anti-penetration ability than the longitudinal wood. However, as the cushion material, the transverse wood exhibits lower structural strength than that of the longitudinal wood. It indicates that the meso-structure of wood dominates the anti-penetration performance, as penetration drastically reduces the interaction surface area.

Figure 10: Dissection of the wood after shot

The dynamic compressive strength, R , is used to quantitatively represent the anti-penetration ability of the wood. The core of bullet has the main contribution for the wood penetration for the jacket and lead filler become debris and have little effect for wood penetration. The core of bullet has little deformation through 4mm 06Cr19Ni10 steel plate, it could be assumed as rigid. The penetration velocity of the wood could be predicted by Equation (1), as listed in Table 5. According to the dynamic cavity expansion theory^[8,9], the DOP in wood could be expressed as

$$P = \frac{2M_c}{\pi d_c^2 N^* \rho_t} \ln\left(1 + \frac{N^* \rho_t V_0^2}{R}\right) \quad (3)$$

Here M_c is the mass of the core, $M_c=3.6\text{g}$. d_c is the diameter of the core, $d_c=5.8\text{mm}$. N^* is the nose factor of the core, $N^*=0.251$. ρ_t is the density of wood, $\rho_t=1490\text{kg/m}^3$ ^[5]. Based on Equation (3), the dynamic compressive strength could be fitted, i.e., $R_H=107.9\text{MPa}$ for the transverse wood and $R_L=67.7\text{MPa}$ for the longitudinal wood. The comparison of DOP between test and theoretical prediction is listed in Table 5 and Fig. 11. The deviation is less than 11%. The higher dynamic compressive strength of the transverse wood quantitatively implies its better ability to resist the penetration of bullet than the longitudinal wood.

Case No.	Wood Type	Thickness mm	Impact Velocity m/s	Penetration Velocity m/s	DOP in wood		
					Test mm	Prediction mm	Deviation %
M-3	Transverse	195.5	749	547	117	130	11
M-5	Transverse	195.0	756	557	144	132	-8
M-15	Transverse	155.8	753	552	128	131	2
M-16	Transverse	155.0	753	552	136	131	-4
M-9	Longitudinal	199.1	750	548	168	181	8
M-10	Longitudinal	199.3	771	577	200*	187	-7

Table 5: Comparison of DOP between test and theoretical prediction

Figure 11: Comparison of DOP between test and theoretical prediction

4 CONCLUSIONS

The anti-penetration performance of the sandwich target made of thin steel plates and wood against 7.62mm ordinary bullet is experimentally studied in the present paper. The steel plates are firstly shot by the bullet and their ballistic limit velocities are fitted according to the Recht-Ipson model, i.e., 511.7m/s, 498.6m/s and 684.3m/s separately for 4mm, 8mm 06Cr19Ni10 and 8mm 30CrMoA steel plates. The bullet could not perforate the 16mm 30CrMoA steel plate.

The sandwich target could not be perforated in the present paper. The bullet applies circumferential pressure along the penetration trajectory. No tearing surface appears in the longitudinal wood after penetration but the weak bonding surface devulses in the transverse wood. The dissection of wood after penetration exhibits that the transverse fibres are broken in transverse wood and the fibres are

pushed aside in the longitudinal wood along the ballistic trajectory. The Depth of Penetration (DOP) in longitudinal wood is higher than that in the transverse wood. Based on the dynamic cavity expansion model, the dynamic compressive strength of the transverse and longitudinal wood are fitted as 107.9MPa and 67.7MPa, separately, which quantitatively represents that the anti-penetration ability of transverse wood is better than that of the longitudinal wood.

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